

A cornerstone of European microelectronics: Minalogic is driving digital sovereignty and reindustrialisation through collaborative innovation

Best practice category

Partner collaboration and open ecosystems; Funding and policy; Skills

Stakeholder group

Associations and trade organisations

Value chain position

R&D, Chip Design, Fabrication

General Information

Minalogic is one of the major microelectronics hubs in Europe, it was founded in 2005 and is headquartered in the **Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region**, with strong roots in the Grenoble area. An important French innovation hub, the cluster represents a global benchmark for digital technologies. Thanks to its strong position among European microelectronics clusters, Minalogic plays a strategic role in addressing the challenges of reindustrialisation, digital transformation, technological sovereignty, and sustainable development. Its key competencies range from chip design to micro and nano-manufacturing, packaging, and testing to equipment. It also has strong expertise in the fields of cybersecurity, optics-photonics, artificial intelligence, and creative industries. The cluster has over 450 members, including more than 380 innovative companies, universities, research centers, investors, and financial institutions, thus covering the entire value chain of the digital sector. In this way, it supports qualified connections between members and promotes growth opportunities at regional, national, and European level. Over the years, Minalogic has supported more than 1,000 R&D projects, contributing to the mobilisation of €2.9 billion in research and development investment, of which €1.2 billion came from public funding. The cluster focuses on Innovation, assisting the development and funding of research projects, and business, promoting international growth and business networking between technology suppliers and buyers also through open innovation events.

Activities and best practices

- Minalogic acts as a primary catalyst for cross-border cooperation within the European microelectronics landscape. Active since 2012 within the Silicon Europe ecosystem, he is co-founder of the Silicon Europe Alliance, which today brings together clusters of 10 European countries. It also held the presidency twice, in 2016 and in 2024. Through this strategic alliance, Minalogic facilitates transnational collaborations in R&D and business, increases the international visibility of businesses and represents the interests of the ecosystem at the European Commission, contributing in a concrete way to the implementation of the European Chips Act. Minalogic also coordinated European initiatives such as the European Commission-funded Silicon Eurocluster project that includes all the clusters of the Silicon Europe Alliance. The project supports R&D and the green transition of SMEs. The cluster was also awarded with Gold Label for Cluster Excellence two times, the last one in 2016.

- The cluster is also active in skills development, contributing to European technological sovereignty and human capital. A key example of this strategic mission is the launch of ASTEERICS, the French Center of Expertise for Semiconductors, scheduled for January 2026, in which Minalogic plays a leading role. This initiative is designed to help startups and SMEs integrate advanced European technologies, such as FD-SOI, GaN and SiC into their products to improve their performance and energy efficiency. Through ASTEERICS, Minalogic offers business awareness sessions, technical support and direct access to European excellence, including design tools, pilot lines and foundries.
- Minalogic connects universities, research centers, and businesses directly to transform ideas into industrial solutions. Collaborating for example with the Université Grenoble Alpes and the MIAI Cluster IA, the hub organises networking opportunities and partnerships between public and private sectors that simplify the transition of expertise from laboratories to the market. Through the European hub MinaSmart, and together with scientific partners such as CEA and Inria, the cluster accompanies SMEs and startups in technology transfer, ensuring that excellent research becomes a competitive advantage for the local industry.

Challenges addressed with this practice

Minalogic contributes to the strengthening of the European semiconductor ecosystem by promoting structured collaborations between industry, research and clusters at European level. It supports SMEs and startups in accessing finance, infrastructure and advanced technologies, accelerating the transformation of research into industrial solutions. Furthermore, it strengthens skills and human capital, supporting technological sovereignty both at the regional and national level, and European reindustrialisation.